

Corporate Governance and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Indian Hospitality Industry

Rinkesh Kumar* and Dinabandhu Mukhopadhyay**

The purpose of this paper is to examine the relationship between corporate governance and performance of the organization in listed Indian hospitality firms using the corporate governance index. The corporate governance annual reports and financial reports of 236 organizations on the basis of random sampling method are selected from Center for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) database. The study uses Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) of corporate governance index of the selected listed companies. The results of the study establish a significant relationship between corporate governance index and financial performance of the selected firms. The corporate governance index, viz., Board Size (BS), Board Duality (BD), Women Director on Board (WD), Independent Director (ID), Non-Independent Director (NID), Executive Director (ED), Non-Executive Director (NED), Total Committee (Tc), and Number of Independent Directors in Total Committee (NoIDTc) played a significant role in the organizational performance of hospitality firms. The results of the study recommend compliance of corporate governance norms by the firms for achieving better financial results. The mandatory corporate governance compliance as per Clause 49 of 2013 Act ensures better governance of firms and can ensure transparency, professionalism, merit and objectivity in the functioning. Good governance ensures better financial results for the firms.

Introduction

Compliance of Corporate Governance (CG) policy and its attribute in a firm is to achieve its long-term corporate goals and to enhance its stakeholder value. The best practices of CG include a firm commitment and adoption of ethical practices as per the rule of the land in which the firm is operating. The *laissez-faire* trade nowadays provides an edge to the organizations to prove their customer loyalty and to maximize profit. Santiso (2001) explained the integrals of CG as threats and challenges in policy implementation of a firm. As per Shleifer and Vishny (1997), CG as a set of systems, principles and processes follows a set of guidelines to direct and control the company to fulfil its goals and objectives. CG is a framework, according to Fama and Jensen (1983), to ensure accountability, fair practices and transparency through its board of directors which has also been validated by Afsharipour (2011). Love *et al.* (2002) explained

* Research Scholar, School of Business, Faculty of Management, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, Katra, Jammu, India; and is the corresponding author. E-mail: rinkesh9@hotmail.com

** Dean, School of Business, Faculty of Management, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, Katra, Jammu, India. E-mail: mukhopadhyay.dinabandhu@gmail.com

the role of firm's stakeholders including financiers, customers, management, employees, government and the community at large to deliver the set results of the organization. CG's values, business conduct and procedures and processes customize the direction and control and the mechanism of functions among the shareholders, directors, employees, auditors and the management, as per Cadbury (2000). Good governance of business organizations is ensured through a mechanism of rules and practices commonly known as Corporate Governance (CG) as reported by Abdo and Fisher (2007) and Arora and Sharma (2016). The CG mechanism is directly under the control of the State under a broad framework in the form of Companies Act, 1956 which was replaced with Companies Act, 2013 in a partial manner. The basic desire of CG is to have a mechanism of systems of checks and balances through mandatory and non-mandatory regulations enshrined in Clause 49 of the Companies Act.

Corporate Governance in Listed Indian Hospitality Firms

The concept of CG in India is however linked to ancient and medieval times, but its modern form is not very old. CG was discussed as a part of integral policy of the state for organizations to operate and add value in Kautilya's *Arthashastra*, Machiavelli's *The Prince* (1505) and Plato's *The Republic*. In its modern form, CG in India is based on the Anglo-Saxon model of the US and UK. Although the Companies Act, 1956 regulates the working of the firm, when codified in 2000, Clause 49 was enshrined with CG to look into equity listing agreement for public listed companies. The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) regulates and controls the security market as a statutory body of Government of India. The CII Code, Kumar Mangalam Birla Committee, Naresh Chandra Committee, Narayana Murthy Committee, CII Task force on Corporate Governance 2009, Corporate Governance Voluntary Guidelines 2009 were some of the attempts to strengthen the working of firms with respect to its corporate governance. The wakeup call in India for CG was given by the post-economic liberalization period which concentrated on Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization (LPG). The Companies Act, 2013 ultimately changed the working style of the corporates. SEBI Clause 49 of listing agreement did allow companies to practice good CG, which came into existence after being introduced by Indian Stock Exchange on December 31, 2005 and which also contains statutory and non-mandatory requirements and provisions of the Companies Act, 1956. The Companies Act, 2013 has a dedicated chapter on corporate governance with Clause 49 as a robust system of CG. Prior to the Companies Act, 2013, the government reforms were piecemeal (Gill *et al.*, 2012).

Hospitality is a discipline of culture and practice, according to Lashley *et al.* (2007), that lack studies related to CG in detail. Gupta *et al.* (2003) made an attempt to study the disclosure and compliance practices of 30 listed hospitality companies at Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and reported that firms provided information about all the desired dimensions but reporting practices varied and mandatory provisions of CG were not complied with. Sharma and Singh (2009) found only 50% compliance of the Corporate Governance Index (CGI) as per Clause 49 that was made by the hospitality firms. Sharma *et al.* (2009) also reiterated that all listed firms have complete agreement with mandatory CG practices as per Clause 49 but the disclosure on non-mandatory practices was disappointing. Bhasin (2010) and Bhardwaj and Rao (2014) also found gaps in the compliance of CG as per Clause 49. Notwithstanding the growth and

emergence of tourism and hospitality sector witnessing a prudent investment by national and international hospitality firms in public listing, the sector has been neglected for reasons unforeseen.

India, being a land of hospitality, treats its guests as God (*Athithi Devo Bhava*). The Latin word *Hospes*, the origin of hospitality, speaks volumes about the nature of modern hospitality. Hospitality was considered as pragmatic by Lashey (2000) in his Six Approach Theory. Lashley and Morrison (2000) later described hospitality, taking into account the three domains, social, private and commercial environment, but categorized it as a commercial activity. The Hospitality Context Model proposed by Statlery (2002) opposed the three domain model of Lashley and Morrison (2000) and categorized hospitality as a relationship of sellers and buyers, the relationship being economic rather than philanthropic. These were some of the failed attempts to satisfy academicians and researchers defining the nature of hospitality. Lashley *et al.* (2007) viewed hospitality as a discipline of culture and practice, whereas Hemmington (2007) proposed five key dimensions of hospitality stimulating all the five senses. Pizam and Shani (2009) stressed the dependence of hospitality on other industries for its growth, despite being the world's oldest, largest and most important industry.

Literature Review

The limited literature available in the hospitality sector makes its study more predisposed to sectors of similar nature. The performance index of the hospitality industry on the Bombay Stock Exchange, as reported by Gordon and Gupta (2003), established the role of CG index as a tool for organizational development in terms of its financial and legal framework, also validated by Jauhari (2009) for the unorganized sector and by Dahlstrom *et al.* (2009) for the franchising industry. Post the Satyam and Kingfisher debacles in India, steps to improve CG by establishing more stringent measures to strengthen the existing corporate law in order to regain public trust, economic stability and investor confidence in the system were initiated across the globe, which has been analyzed by Ann and Rezaee (2012). Shleifer and Vishny (1997) explain the corporation's assurance of finance supply for maximum return on their investment controlled the residual claims also reported by Epps and Cereola (2008). The studies on board size and capital structure by Lipton and Lorsch (1992), Berger and David (1997) and Yermack (2004) established a negative leverage due to the presence of external directors, but change in external directors' incentives increased the wealth creation and financial position of the firm. Board size and financial position plays a significant role in the determination of control in relation to the practices established by an organization and seen as a mechanism to control the organization, as stated by Kim (2005) and Hassan *et al.* (2008). The major attributes of CG, i.e., conformance and performance, are seen as monitoring, supervising and being accountable to different stakeholders by performance contribution of managers as reported by Hassan and Halbouni (2013). CG acts as a tool of administration, implementation of CG codes and principles may or may not result in reforms, but literature establishes causal relationship between CG and firm performance taking into account single governance variable, according to the studies of Yermack (1996), and Bhagat and Black (2001). But Gompers *et al.* (2003), Brown and Caylor (2006) and Core *et al.* (2006) also suggested that due to the complex nature of CG, the CG index should be taken into account while studying the impact of CG on firm performance. The other argument

of some of the researchers that good CG results in better corporate performance leading to better financial results, advocated reforms in the field of CG. According to Buallay *et al.* (2017), there are some studies that suggested that there is no significant relationship between CG and firm performance. Although the relationship between CG and firm performance has been studied and established in most of the developed countries by studies such as Hermalin and Weisbach (1991), Barnhart *et al.* (1994), Kang and Shivdasani (1995), Gompers *et al.* (2003), Judge *et al.* (2003), Bauer *et al.* (2004), Christopher and Lee (2004), Bhagat and Bolton (2008) and Guest (2008), still it is in its infancy in a developing country like India and need to be studied for CG principles and its impact on firm performance for hospitality firms. Most of the studies have been made in manufacturing, automobile and banking sectors but not in the hospitality industry, as reported by Jauhari (2009), Gunjan and Jauhari (2012) and Price *et al.* (2015). Some researchers have also tried to study the challenges and strategic and financial issues in the hospitality sector, but due to the small sample size, it restricted the hospitality sector research in India, as per the studies of Dwivedi and Jain (2005), Ghosh (2006), Garg (2007) and Jackling and Johl (2009). But in the manufacturing sector, valuation of the CG index has been established by the studies of Ghosh (2006), Garg (2007) and Kohli and Saha (2008).

Objective

This study aims to establish the relationship between CG index and the performance of the organization in the listed Indian hospitality firms using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) from the dataset of Center for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) for the years 2006 to 2015.

Data and Methodology

The present paper analyzes the CG reports as per CG index and financial governance reports of 236 listed hospitality firms. The data is obtained from primary sources from the listed hospitality firms through a questionnaire (see Appendix) prepared based on the CG index and financial performance data of the firms and from secondary source from Center for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) from 2006 to 2015 from 236 firms. The data was collected through random sampling method. The CG annual performance report and financial reports were analyzed based on the facts and exhibits provided by these companies over the last 10 years in their annual report as on March 31, 2015. The CG index variables were divided into CG variables and financial performance variables (Table 1).

The CG index variables and financial performance variables were confirmed based on the second order construct validity using Principal Axis Factoring with Promax rotation of CFA. The results confirmed 10 observed variables of CG index and seven 7 observed variables of financial variables which were taken as latent variables during the analysis. The measurement model is shown in Figure 1. 17 variables out of total 25 variables were taken for the second order construct. The variables having multicollinearity were excluded and the factor loading above 0.4 were included in the construct order value of the measurement model as per studies conducted by Osborne *et al.* (2008).

The measurement model shows all the 17 factors to be inter-correlated. The CG index variables and financial performance variables which were above the significant values (0.4) were

Table 1: CG Index and Financial Performance Variables	
Corporate Governance Variables	Financial Performance Variables
Board Size (<i>BS</i>)	Total Assets (<i>TA</i>)
Board Duality (<i>BD</i>)	Sales (<i>S</i>)
Women Director (<i>WD</i>)	Reserves and Funds (<i>R&F</i>)
Independent Director (<i>ID</i>)	Profit After Tax (<i>PAT</i>)
Non-Independent Director (<i>NID</i>)	Cash Profit (<i>CP</i>)
Executive Director (<i>ED</i>)	Net Profit Margin (<i>NPM</i>)
Non-Executive Director (<i>NED</i>)	Paid up Capital Equity (<i>PuCE</i>)
Total Committee (<i>Tc</i>)	Return on Assets (<i>RoA</i>)
Independent Directors in total Committee (<i>NoIDTc</i>)	Return on Equity (<i>RoE</i>)
Corporate Social Responsibility (<i>CSR</i>)	Leverage (Debt/Equity Ratio) (<i>Lev</i>)
Firm Age (<i>FA</i>)	Return on Capital Employed (<i>RoCE</i>)
Year of Incorporation (<i>Yol</i>)	Tobin's <i>Q</i> (<i>Tq</i>)
	Market Capitalization (<i>MktCap</i>)

further taken for regression analysis to establish the effectiveness of CG in the hospitality industry. The variables left out from CG index were *FA*, and *PAT* and *TA* from financial performance index. Table 2 shows the fit statistics of measurement model.

Results and Discussion

Panel Data Analysis

Analysis of CG, taking into account CG index variables and financial performance variables, is expressed for panel data as per the following equation:

$$CG = \alpha + \beta_1 BS + \beta_2 BD + \beta_3 WD + \beta_4 ID + \beta_5 NID + \beta_6 ED + \beta_7 NED + \beta_8 Tc + \beta_9 NoIDTc + \beta_{10} RoCE + \beta_{11} Lev + \beta_{12} ROE + \beta_{13} ROA + \beta_{14} NPM + \beta_{15} ni(Dn) + \mu_t \quad \dots(1)$$

where *Dn* = Dummy Variable for the Year, *n* and *ni* = No. of Years

Random Effect GLS Regression

Number of observation = 845, Number of group = 113, $R^2 = 0.5167$, $\chi^2 = 761.15$ and Probability = 0.0000 (95% conf. interval)

Corporate Governance Variables

The results in Table 3 establish that *ID*, *NID*, *ED*, *NED*, *NPM*, *ROA*, *ROE* and *Lev* values are significant with the R^2 value as 0.5167 and the *p*-value 0.00 ($p < 0.01$) with a Chi-Square (χ^2)

Table 2: Fit Statistics of the Measurement Model

Fit Statistics	Recommended	Obtained	Fit Statistics	Recommended	Obtained
χ^2		761.15	NFI	>0.90	0.91
df		988	RFI	>0.90	0.93
χ^2 Significance	$p < = 0.05$	0.000	CFI	>0.90	0.92
χ^2 /df	<5.0	2.96	TLI	>0.90	0.91
GFI	>0.90	0.91	RMSEA	>0.05	0.08
AGFI	>0.90	0.92	RMR	<0.02	0.004

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistics	Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistics
<i>BS</i>	-0.0201247	-1.06	<i>Lev</i>	0.0123328	3.21
<i>WD</i>	0.0072485	0.12	<i>RoCE</i>	0.0053488	0.99
<i>BD</i>	-0.0459669	-0.39	2007	-0.0574748	-0.47
<i>ID</i>	0.1189359	1.98	2008	-0.0870801	-0.72
<i>NID</i>	0.0345706	2.26	2009	-0.1187024	-1.00
<i>ED</i>	0.1004907	2.18	2010	-0.1675194	-1.41
<i>NED</i>	0.0470095	2.16	2011	-0.1585614	-1.32
<i>Tc</i>	0.0144033	0.29	2012	-0.3586299	-2.91
<i>NoIDTc</i>	-0.0829685	-1.34	2013	-0.2349814	-1.88
<i>NPM</i>	0.0003819	9.58	2014	-0.4148278	-3.07
<i>ROA</i>	0.0964308	10.27	2015	-0.8006582	-5.33
<i>ROE</i>	0.0044036	7.86	Constant	2.327388	17.32

value of 761.15, which signifies that the model is significant. The variables *ID*, *NID*, *ED*, *NED*, *NPM*, *ROA*, *ROE* and *LEV* play a significant role in the compliance of the norms of CG of a firm. The results also establish that as the compliance of the CG increases, the financial performance of the firm also increases. *BS*, *WD* and *NoIDTc* have a negative coefficient value having a negative impact on the compliance of the CG, while all other variables have a positive impact on CG. *BS*, *WD* and *NoIDTc* do not significantly impact the working of the firm and they can be considered to be adopted for the purpose of fulfilling the norms of the compliance of CG. *ID*, *NID*, *ED*, *NED* have a significant relationship between *NPM*, *ROA*, *ROE* and *LEV* of the firm, as per the results of the study and compliance of the CG index increases the financial viability of the firm.

The analysis of the data obtained from primary and secondary sources for the years 2006-2015 establishes the role of CG in the hospitality sector. The results also establish a significant relationship between compliance of CG and financial performance. However, *BS*, *WD* and *NoIDTc* have shown a negative impact on CG of the firm. These CG variables make significant contribution in compliance of CG of the hospitality firm. The financial variables *RoCE*, *Lev*, *ROE* and *ROA* have a positive relationship with compliance of CG establishing that CG compliance increases the productivity and effectiveness of the organizations in terms of its financial performance. The regression results between CG and the independent variables indicate that the year taken as the dummy variable has a significant impact on CG minimizing the impact of the establishment year of the firm. The results indicate that *ID*, *NID*, *ED*, *NED*, *RoCE*, *Lev*, *ROE* and *ROA* values were significant ($p < 0.01$) and had significantly impacted the CG of the

firms. The results also confirm the impact of CG on the financial performance of the hospitality firms, as CG has a significant positive relationship with financial performance obtained from the regression model.

Conclusion

The study examines the relationship between CG and performance of the organization in listed Indian hospitality firms. The authors tested the CG determinants to establish a relationship between practices of CG and financial performance and effectiveness of boards, which plays a significant role in exhibiting transparency, consistency, accountability, responsibility and fairness of the working of the firms. Compliance of CG increases the firms' financial performance enabling trust building between its shareholders and financial institutions. Since hospitality is a significant sector in the contribution to foreign exchange, better display of compliance of CG by the hospitality firms would attract more Foreign Investment (FI). The display of professionalism in the governance of tourism and hospitality firms will not only build the trust to get required capital for growth of the hospitality industry through FI but would also have a far-reaching impact on the preservation of historical and cultural resources of the country. The CG best practices in hospitality firms shall develop a culture of continuous learning, enabling effective oversight of the management and value creation for its stakeholders. The trust among the shareholders and the management can be built through a culture of disseminating right information about the workings of the organization and about the books of accounts enabling investor confidence in the firm's financial results. The compliance of CG by hospitality firms would strengthen the corporate sector of the hospitality industry, which is still dominated by the family entrepreneurs. The development of corporate sector in hospitality industry would see a rise in institutional building in the service sector. Good governance of hospitality firms would ensure more efficient utilization of the available resources, better inflow of capital for development of the hospitality sector, higher quality employment opportunity and efficient development of regional capital market, creating more economic value for the country. The compliance of CG by hospitality firms shall protect the shareholders' rights by ensuring profitability. Effective CG helps to cultivate the culture of integrity in the firm's working, leading to positive performance and a sustainable business model and to developing a strong competitive business advantage for the firm. □

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Appendix

Questionnaire

Part I: Demographic Profile of the Organization

1. Name of the Company:
2. Address of the Company:
3. Year of Establishment:
4. Nature of Company Business:
 Hospitality and Service Any Other
If any other, Please specify: _____
5. Name of the Participant/Executive:
6. Total no. of subsidiary companies of your organization:
7. Total number of employees in your company:
8. Total number of offices of your company:
9. Ownership structure of your company
 Sole Proprietorship Partnership
 Limited Partnership Limited Liability Company (LLC)
 Corporation (For Profit) Nonprofit Corporation (Not-for-profit)
 Cooperative
10. What is the male and female employees ratio in your company?
11. Name of solicitor(s) of your company:
12. Name of Auditor(s) of your company:

Appendix (Cont.)

Part II: Corporate Governance

1. Total no. of directors on board:
2. No. of executive directors:
3. Please specify the term for appointing executive directors?
 - 2 Years
 - 3 Years
 - 5 Years
 - Any other
4. No. of non-executive directors:
5. No. of independent directors:
6. Total no. of women directors on the board of directors:
7. What is the maximum tenure of independent directors on board?
 - 2 Years
 - 4 Years
 - 5 Years
 - Any other
8. Should the independent directors on board be appointed twice in your company?
 - Yes
 - No
9. Composition of the Board: **Executive : Non-Executive**
 - 50:50
 - 75:25
 - Any Other. Please Specify _____
10. Your company have key managerial personnel in the form of managing director, or chief executive officer or manager and in their absence, a full-time director, company secretary and chief financial officer.
 - Yes
 - No
11. The chairman and CEO/MD of your organization are same.
 - Yes
 - No

Appendix (Cont.)

12. How many board meetings are held in a Financial Year in your company?
- One Two
 Three Four
 Any Other
13. Does your company advise that the office of the chairman and the office of the MD be filled by different persons?
- Yes No
14. If yes, please rate as below.
- Highly Preferred Moderately Preferred
 Less Preferred Not Preferred
- If no, please specify the reason.
-
-
15. Should your company appoint nominee directors as member of its board of directors?
- Yes No
16. Do your company feel that expenses on nominee directors a burden on your company?
- Yes No
- If yes, please rate the burden as under.
- 0-25% 25-50%
 50-75% Above 75%
17. Does your company advocate the rotation of nominee director(s) on board of the company?
- Yes No
- If yes, please specify the term.
- 1 Year 2 Year
 3 Years 4 Years
- If no, please specify the reason.
- Financial Institutions/ Banks may not agree
 Continuity and consistency may not be there
 Non availability of suitable person
 It may not be effective A costly affair

Appendix (Cont.)

18. Does your company prefer professionals like CA, CS, CMA or management professionals as its nominee directors?
- Yes No
- If yes, please indicate your preference.
- CA CS
 CMA MBA
 Engineers Others
19. Does your company advocate the rotation of auditors for overall improvement in quality of financial reporting and independence of statutory auditors?
- Yes No
- If yes, please specify the duration.
- 2 Years 3 Years
 5 Years
20. Does your company prefer audit committee comprising solely of non-executive directors?
- Yes No
21. What is the total number of committees in your company?
22. Kindly mark the committees of your organization as per the Companies Act, 2013.
- Audit Committee Nomination and Remuneration Committee
 Risk Management Committee Corporate Social Responsibility Committee
 Stakeholders Relationship Committee
 Independent Directors Committee
23. Is the audit committee chairman of the company an independent director?
- Yes No
24. What is the total number of members in your company audit committee?
25. Are the audit committee members of your organization accounting and finance experts?
- Yes No
26. The audit committee members consists of:
- Non-Executive Directors Executive and Non-Executive Directors
 Non-Executive and outside Consultants
 Nominee Directors only Others

Appendix (Cont.)

27. The nomination and remuneration committee members of your organization are non-executive directors of the board.	☐ Yes	☐ No
28. Is chairman of nomination and remuneration committee of your organization an independent director?	☐ Yes	☐ No
29. Is the chairman of your organization a member of nomination and remuneration committee?	☐ Yes	☐ No
30. Is chairman of the nomination and remuneration committee also the chairman of the company in your organization?	☐ Yes	☐ No
31. Are your organization board members Serious Fraud Investigation Officers (SIO) set up by Ministry of Corporate Affairs?	☐ Yes	☐ No
32. Has your organization laid down a risk management policy for identifying risk in the competitive area which may threaten the existence of the company?	☐ Yes	☐ No
33. Does the board of your organization issue a directors responsibility statement under Section 134 of the Companies Act, 2013 about the compliance of the provision of the Act?	☐ Yes	☐ No
34. Does your organization CSR committee have an independent director?	☐ Yes	☐ No
35. Does your organization have a vigil mechanism for directors and employees?	☐ Yes	☐ No
36. Does your organization safeguard persons against victimization of false charges and frauds?	☐ Yes	☐ No
37. Does your organization include Vigil mechanism report as the part of the Annual Board Report?	☐ Yes	☐ No

Appendix (Cont.)

38. Is your organization Stakeholders Relationship Committee chairman a non-executive director?
- Yes No
39. Does the power of your organization lie in:
- Board of Directors Chief Executive Officer
- Both
40. Does a two/three tier board provide a better form of governance?
- Two tier Three tier
- Any other
- If any other, please specify _____

Part III: Financial Information

1. Do your company generate the financial report of the organization as per National Financial Reporting Authority of the Companies Act, 2013?
- Yes No
2. Does your company have uniform financial year ending on March 31st of every year?
- Yes No
3. Is your company listed in any of the Stock Exchanges?
- Yes No
- If yes, please specify.
- BSE NSE
- Both Any Other
4. Kindly provide the following details for the financial year ended on March 31, 2016.
- Gross Non-Current Assets Net Current Assets
- Sales Reserves
- Net Profit Dividend distributed
- Cash Profit Earnings Per Share
- Debt/Equity Ratio Equity
- Debts Provision for Taxation
- Dividend Yield

Appendix (Cont.)

5.	The objective of your board is to:	
	☐ Maximize Shareholders Value	☐ Customer Satisfaction and Delight
	☐ Good Governance	☐ All of the Above
6.	Does your company issue a Consolidated Financial Statement (CFS) under Section 129 of the Companies Act, 2013?	
	☐ Yes	☐ No
7.	Is there any presence of insider trading practice in your company?	
	☐ Yes	☐ No
8.	If serial No. 7 is yes then, does your company have a strict action laid down against the insider trading involved personnel?	
	☐ Yes	☐ No
	☐ Can't say	
9.	Does your company have any regulation on related party transactions?	
	☐ Yes	☐ No
10.	Does your company provide employee stock ownership option to its employees?	
	☐ Yes	☐ No
Part IV: Governance, Corporate Social Responsibility and Green Initiative		
1.	Mark 1-8 for the following characteristics of good governance in your organization:	
	☐ Participation	☐ Accountability
	☐ Consensus	☐ Transparency
	☐ Responsive	☐ Efficiency and Effectiveness
	☐ Equitable and Inclusive	☐ Following the Rules of the law
2.	Your organization feels that the corporate governance model should be based on:	
	☐ Rule based	☐ Voluntary base
	☐ Combination of both	
3.	Is corporate governance in India more governed by law?	
	☐ Yes	☐ No
4.	If yes, to what extent?	
	☐ More than 80%	☐ 60-80%
	☐ 40-60%	☐ Less than 40%

Appendix (Cont.)

5. How do you consider your company's transparency rating in your annual report?
- Excellent Good
 Satisfactory Poor
6. According to your companies Mission and Vision statement, the decisions of corporate leaders should be based on
- Economic consideration Customer orientation
 Society orientation Combination of all
Any other, Please specify _____
7. Kindly rank the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities undertaken by your company from 1-10.
- Eradicating extreme hunger and poverty
 Promotion of education
 Promoting gender equality and empowering women
 Reducing child mortality and improving maternal health
 Combating human immunodeficiency virus, acquired immune deficiency syndrome, malaria and other diseases
 Ensuring environmental sustainability
 Employment enhancing vocational skills
 Social business projects
 Contribution to the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund or any other fund set-up by the Central Government or the State governments for socio-economic development and relief, and funds for the welfare of the scheduled castes and Tribes, other backward classes, minorities and women
 Any other activities
8. What % of total net profit is spent in your company for CSR activities?
- Less than 1% 1%
 2% More than 2%
9. Do you feel that the rights of shareholders are protected under the Companies Act, 2013 more than ever before?
- Yes No
10. If yes, to what extent.
- 0-25% 25-50%
 50-75% Above 75%

Appendix (Cont.)

11. How well informed are the managers with regard to the environmental changes around them?
- Highly knowledgeable Reasonably informed
- Moderately informed Less informed
12. Does your company use recycle waste as a raw material for producing new goods?
- Yes No
13. Does your company promotes green and clean environment initiative?
- Yes No
14. If yes, kindly provide the list of initiatives being followed by your company.
- A .
-
- B .
-
- C .
-
- D .
-
- E.
-
15. Does your company feel that CSR activities can bring a positive change in society?
- Yes No
- Can't Say
16. Does your company believe that Green CSR activities can bring sustainability of the ecosystem and environment?
- Yes No
- Can't Say
17. Does your company practice Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) for buildings and new projects?
- Yes No
- Can't Say

Appendix (Cont.)

18. Is your company ISO 14001:2015 certified?

- Yes No

19. If no, has your company applied for the same for Green initiative?

- Yes No
 Can't Say

20. Does your company feel that the expenditure on CSR activities is a wastage of money and time?

- Yes No
 Can't Say

Conclusion

Do you wish to share any other information on the topic of study? If yes, please write below.

Suggestions

Please offer your valuable suggestion in ensuring good corporate governance by the corporate sector in India.

Date:

Signature

Reference # 04J-2021-07-02-01